

STRITBOLDA TEXNIK-TAKTIK KO‘NIKMALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA JISMONIY SIFATLAR VA PSIXOLOGIK BARQARORLIKNING ROLI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada stritbol o‘yinida talaba-sportchilarning texnik-taktik ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishda jismoniy tayyorgarlik va psixologik barqarorlikning o‘zaro integratsiyasi tadqiq etiladi. Stritbolning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari — kichik maydon sharoitida yuqori tezlik va ruhiy bosim ostida qaror qabul qilish jarayonlari - tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, jismoniy sifatlar va psixologik tayyorgarlik darajasi texnik usullarning samaradorligini bevosita belgilab beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: talabalar, stritbol, jismoniy sifatlar, texnik-taktik tayyorgarlik, psixologik barqarorlik, integratsiya, musobaqa faoliyati.

Kirish. Bugungi kunda talaba-yoshlar o‘rtasida sportning ommaviy turlaridan biri bo‘lgan stritbolga qiziqish sezilarli darajada ortib bormoqda. Stritbol nafaqat jismoniy salomatlikni mustahkamlash vositasi, balki bo‘ljak mutaxassislarining kasbiy faoliyati uchun zarur bo‘lgan chidamlilik va tezkorlik kabi sifatlarni tarbiyalovchi muhim omildir. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar sport tayyorgarligi tizimida jismoniy, texnik, taktik va psixologik vositalarning uzviy bog‘liqligini ta’kidlaydi. Shu bois, stritbol o‘yinida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun faqat texnik usullarni egallash yetarli emas; sportchi yuqori funksional tayyorgarlik va kuchli iroda sohibi bo‘lishi lozim.

Muammoning dolzarbligi.

Stritbol musobaqalari davomida o‘yinchilar organizmning barcha tizimlarini safarbar qiluvchi jismoniy yuklamalarni boshdan kechiradilar. O‘yin maydonining kichikligi harakatlar dinamikasini oshiradi, bu esa sportchidan tezkor manyovr qilishni talab etadi. Mas’uliyatli musobaqalarda yuzaga keladigan stressli vaziyatlar chuqur emotsional zo‘riqishlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Kuchli psixologik barqarorlik va yaxshi jismoniy holat sportchiga ana shunday yuklamalarni yengishda yordam beradi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi.

Stritbolda texnik-taktik harakatlarni o‘rgatish jarayonida jismoniy, psixologik va texnik tayyorgarlik o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlikning ahamiyatini aniqlash va ilmiy asoslash.

Tadqiqot metodlari.

Jismoniy tayyorgarlik ko‘rsatkichlarini aniqlash uchun test sinovlari.

1. Texnik-taktik mahorat darajasini baholash.
2. Psixologik barqarorlikni kuzatish metodlari.
3. Statistik ma’lumotlarni qiyosiy tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot Samarqand davlat arxitektura-qurilish universiteti talaba-sportchilari ishtirokida o‘tkazildi.

Natijalar va tahlil. Ikki yillik kuzatuvlar davomida maxsus tayyorgarlik darajasida sezilarli ijobiy siljishlar aniqlandi:

Jismoniy tayyorgarlik:

Eng katta o‘sish "shuttle run" (shatlli yugurish) va 6 metrga sakrash (ryvok) kabi tezkorlik testlarida kuzatildi.

Texnik tayyorgarlik: 1 daqiqa davomida harakatda to‘p tashlash natijadorligi va “slalom” usulida yugurish ko‘rsatkichlari yaxshilandi. Bu natijalar maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasining oshishi o‘yin harakatlarining umumiy samaradorligiga bevosita ta‘sir qilishini tasdiqlaydi.

Xulosa. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, stritbolda tayyorgarlikning turli jihatlarini o‘zaro muvofiqlashtirish - ya‘ni jismoniy, texnik-taktik, psixologik va funksional tayyorgarlikni birgalikda rivojlantirish - sportchilarning umumiy natijalarini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Yuqori natijalarga erishish faqat maxsus jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish va texnik-taktik harakatlarni o‘rgatish jarayonini integratsiyalash orqali amalga oshiriladi. O‘yin davomidagi barcha harakatlar jismoniy kuchdan tortib psixologik barqarorlikkacha - sportchiga o‘z mahoratini to‘liq namoyish etish imkonini beradi.

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